

Variation in psychopathological terminology: A case study on Body Dysmorphic Disorder

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Representing specialized knowledge in the medical domain implies considering the dynamism of scientific and technological progress. The advancement of knowledge on diseases goes hand in hand with the reconceptualization processes undertaken by experts with consequent conceptual evolutions and possible variations of the terms used to designate medical concepts. Sometimes term variation is the result of a desire to avoid or overcome negative connotations anchored in medical terms, and leads to the creation of less evaluatively charged terms that carry a diminished ideological load.

This study illustrates the case of Body Dysmorphic Disorder (BDD), a relatively under-/misdiagnosed medical condition which has been the object of multiple reconceptualizations by experts. We focus on the analysis of the conceptual evolution of BDD and the consequent variation occurring at the linguistic level. We adopt the theoretical assumption that terminology has a double dimension – conceptual and linguistic. Following on this assumption, the terminologist must examine both the experts' conceptualizations of a given domain and the discourses produced by them in order to effectively represent the specialized knowledge of a specific subject field. To complete the analysis, we present how information about BDD is disseminated to non-experts through the analysis of a corpus of mass-media articles.

Keywords: Body Dysmorphic Disorder, conceptual evolution, connotation, medical terminology, term variation

1. Introduction

Medical terminology can acquire negative connotations (Bowker and Hawkins 2006; Vezzani 2023) which can prompt terminological variation (Daille 2017; Freixa 2022; Dury 2022). The desire to overcome negative implications is, in some cases, the driving force that animates the “neological need” of medical experts to rename concepts whose designation has become charged, over time, with a de-valorizing connotation (Dury 2012, 2013). In other cases, terminological variation is introduced by media professionals in medical discourse for popularization purposes (Ordóñez-López and Nuria 2016). In this context, this study intends to highlight the inter- and transdisciplinary potential of terminology as an effective research area for the optimal conceptual and linguistic representations of specialized knowledge in the medical field. In this paper, we analyze the variation that characterizes medical discourse about BDD, and we investigate its dissemination to non-experts, considering the possible ideological undertones of the terminology used. BDD is a medical condition characterized by “persistent preoccupation with one or more perceived defects or flaws in appearance that are either unnoticeable or only slightly noticeable to others” (American Psychiatric Association 2013), which causes marked functional impairment across multiple aspects of life. BDD affects 1.7% to 2.4% of the general population (Herbst and Jemec 2020), and its impact results in high rates of occupational impairment, unemployment, social dysfunction, and isolation (Phillips et al. 2006a). Moreover, comorbidity studies show a relationship between BDD and major depressive disorder, obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD),

and BDD has been associated with strikingly high rates of suicidality (rates of suicide attempts range from 3%–63%) (Angelakis et al. 2016).

The use of social networks, the visual perception of one's own digital image, and the possibility of using face-altering filters that radically modify perceived defects induce a greater incidence of BDD (Ryding and Kuss 2019), thus revealing underlying societal unrealistic ideologies regarding beauty standards and self-perception. This aspect is relevant in this historical moment in which the COVID-19 pandemic has led to a massive shift toward virtual living for both work and social events. BDD shows a trend toward an increase in symptom severity requiring deep preventive and curative action by healthcare professionals involved in its detection, diagnosis, and treatment, such as psychologists, psychiatrists, and surgeons (Quittkat et al. 2020).

Despite its worldwide prevalence, increasing incidence and considerable impact on social and private life, BDD is a relatively under-/misdiagnosed medical condition (Cororve and Gleaves 2001) which presents a problem of unstable and inconsistent conceptual and linguistic representation within the existing biomedical terminological resources – such as the International Classification of Diseases (ICD),¹ the Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) thesaurus,² and SNOMED Clinical Terms.³ This potentially affects the quality of the diagnosis and treatment of the disorder by healthcare professionals, as well as the comprehension of specialized medical discourse by non-experts, in particular patients, either directly or indirectly involved with the disorder. From a terminological viewpoint, this disorder constitutes an interesting case study in terms of conceptual diachronic evolution and linguistic variation. The study of Cororve and Gleaves (2001) illustrates that this medical condition has been the object of numerous reconceptualizations by medical experts which have led, over time, to the variation of the terms used to designate the concept. In this context, the role of ideology is pivotal in shaping shifts in labels and conceptualizations surrounding BDD, reflecting evolving societal norms and perceptions of beauty and mental health.

This paper has the following objectives:

- 1) To retrace the different medical reconceptualizations of the disorder and frame its linguistic variation by adopting the theoretical assumption and the methodology for terminological work proposed in Costa (2013) and Santos and Costa (2015).
- 2) To analyze how information about BDD is disseminated to non-experts, considering also possible ideological undertones of medical discourse. Based on a corpus specifically made up of mass-media articles, we focus on the popular discourse about BDD and identify term variants, as well as terminological neologisms emerged with reference to this medical condition.

The paper aims to illustrate how medical reconceptualizations impact term variation in specialized and popular medical discourse, particularly those found in mass-media articles. Taking all this into account means conducting a terminological work which also considers possible ideological positioning about specialized knowledge and its transfer to the society.

The remainder of this paper is as follows. Section 2 presents an overview of studies related to variation in terminology, particularly in the medical domain. In section 3, we describe the first research objective discussed above, focusing on the analysis of the conceptual and linguistic dimensions of BDD. Section 4 describes the second research objective, namely how information

¹ <https://www.who.int/standards/classifications/classification-of-diseases>.

² <https://www.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/meshhome.html>.

³ <https://www.snomed.org>.

about BDD is disseminated to non-experts in mass-media articles and the ideological implications of this process. Finally, in section 5 we present our conclusions and describe our future work.

2. Background

Working for the purposes of representing medical terminology means considering the constant evolution of specialized knowledge that characterizes this domain. Its dynamism is due to scientific and technological progress and implies the frequent reconceptualization of pathologies and the possible variation of the terms used to designate medical concepts. An example is provided in León-Araúz (2017, 216):

[...] it was only after the discovery that *Down syndrome* was caused by the presence of an extra chromosome that the term variant *trisomy 21* emerged, which focuses on the causal dimension of the concept. Until then, the variants focused on the discoverer of the disease (John Langdon Down 1828–1896) and the physical attributes of the patients (*mongolism*). This term was eventually suppressed because of its obviously negative connotations.

Indeed, as stated by Kristiansen (2011, 32) with reference to the nature of knowledge: “scientific concepts will be constantly questioned, resulting in a repetitive and revisable process. Consequently, new concepts may emerge, and other concepts may change or even disappear.” Considering the linguistic level, this process can impact the verbalizations of concepts and result in term variation. Taking up the classification proposed in Bowker and Hawkins (2006) regarding the phenomenon of variation in medical terminology, the following state-of-the-art is divided into studies that consider conceptually motivated factors underlying term variation (section 2.1), and linguistically motivated factors behind term variation (section 2.2). Finally, the studies concerning the phenomenon of connotation that can be anchored to medical terms are taken into consideration (section 2.3).

2.1 The conceptual dimension of variation

Analyzing the conceptual dimension in the context of term variation means defining what is meant by conceptual variation, this being one of the research topics of the variationist movement that has characterized terminology science since the late 1990s.

According to Freixa (2022, 401), “conceptual variation” is a type of terminological variation that covers different phenomena of variation affecting a concept, whereas “denominative variation” is strictly related to the variety of designations used for the same concept. Conceptual variation is also one of the main focuses of Freixa and Fernández-Silva (2017), who defend the hypothesis of the unsaturability of concepts. By adopting the philosophical paradigm of experiential realism, they define a concept as a dynamic, flexible cognitive entity that cannot be exhausted (Freixa and Fernández-Silva 2017, 157). In doing so, they call into question the theories and models of cognition developed for general knowledge in cognitive science (see, among others, Rosch (1978), Fillmore (1985), Lakoff and Johnson (1980)), which have been also repropounded in terminology and, therefore, for specialized knowledge (Temmerman 2000; Faber 2012). The authors introduce a subjective dimension (i.e., “subjects’ personal experience” (Freixa and Fernández-Silva 2017, 158)) of the concepts, which makes them variable and unsaturable. Based on this premise, the authors also distinguish between conceptual variation which has no denominative effect (that is, the concept varies over time but the term designating it remains the same), and conceptual variation

which is reflected in denominations (that is, leading to term variation). In line with the same theoretical framework of cognitive science, the authors also explore the motivation behind experts' choice of a term variant (Freixa et al. 2008; Fernández-Silva et al. 2011).

Focusing on the medical domain, Bowker and Hawkins (2006) investigate what drives medical experts to choose one form over another. In particular, they aim to “determine the extent to which lexicalization is the reflection, in language, of the mental processes involved in concept formation and association” (Bowker and Hawkins 2006, 82). Another contribution in this direction is provided by Fernández-Silva (2016, 2022), who studies cognitive and communicative functions of intra-textual term variation in research articles related to the domain of psychology. Based on interviews with domain experts, the author classifies the reasons for term variation based on communicative-stylistic factors – such as avoiding repetitions – or cognitive factors, for example, to favor “conceptual clarity” (Fernández-Silva 2022, 453).

When variation is analyzed with reference to the conceptual dimension, another key research topic is that of the multidimensionality of the concept, a notion that takes on different nuances depending on the scholar using it. In Bowker (2022), multidimensionality is defined as a phenomenon of conceptual classification and refers to the fact that concepts are classified in more than one way within a conceptual system according to different characteristics that one wishes to highlight. In the studies of León-Araúz and Reimerink (2014, 2015) and León-Araúz (2015, 2017), multidimensionality is considered from the perspective of how the choice of a given term activates a specific conceptual dimension in the perceiver (see the above-mentioned example of *Down syndrome*). In line with Fernández-Silva et al. (2011), León-Araúz and Reimerink (2014, 659) state that “multidimensionality also has an impact on term variation, since concepts can be designated in more than one way based on the different characteristics that it possesses”. An example of this specifically related to psychiatry terminology is provided in León-Araúz (2017, 222), where the author illustrates how the term variants *Ganser syndrome*, *nonsense syndrome* and *prison psychosis* are due to conceptual multidimensionality.

In León-Araúz and Reimerink (2014), the authors present how variation is represented in the VariMed⁴ resource specifically designed to support the work of language professionals, in particular specialized translators for the medical domain who are faced with the need to choose among different term variants for the same concept (Tercedor Sánchez et al. 2014; Alarcón-Navío et al. 2016).⁵ Finally, with a view to building useful tools to support the work of specialized translators and technical writers in the medical context, Arlin et al. (2006, 84) show the study of the evolution of concepts and the variation of terms in the medical field, illustrating the example of the term *nephritis* and its variants due to the evolution of medical knowledge.

2.2 The linguistic dimension of variation

In the previous section, we described some cases of variation directly attributable to conceptual-nature factors. According to some scholars, the variation reflected on the linguistic level is always to be considered dependent on the conceptual dimension of terminology:

⁴ <http://varimed.ugr.es>.

⁵ For an analysis of terminological resources that take variation into account, see Vezzani and Di Nunzio (2020) with the description of the multipurpose and multilingual TriMED resource available at <http://purl.org/TriMED>.

term variation should not be regarded as a linguistic phenomenon isolated from conceptual representations, since it is one of the manifestations of the dynamicity of categorization and expression of specialized knowledge (León-Araúz and Reimerink 2014, 659).

Other scholars, however, illustrate variation that is attributable only to linguistic factors, such as Bowker and Hawkins (2006), who show that experts can make linguistically motivated term choices.

One of the main contributions on the causes of denominative variation in terminology is provided by Freixa (2006, 2022). In her typology, she describes not only causes of a cognitive nature (see previous section), but also causes linked to dialectal factors (such as geographical variation), discursive factors (e.g., avoiding repetition, linguistic economy, creativity, emphasis, and expressiveness), and interlinguistic factors (cohabitation of a “local” term and the relevant loanword). Delavigne (2017) adopts a socioterminological stance to analyze term variation in a cancerology corpus in French. In particular, the corpus collects guides for cancer patients, texts from medical books, websites, journals, and texts from Internet medical forums. The author then focuses on different types of variation that occur in the corpus, illustrating examples of diatopic (*hématologue vs hématologiste*) or diastratic variations (*gavage vs nutrition entérale*) (Delavigne 2017, 34). The identification of linguistic patterns underlying term variation is a relevant task for the purposes of natural language processing. In this direction, the study by Daille et al. (1996) constitutes a groundbreaking experimental analysis of the variation of medical terms in a 1.5-million-word medical corpus with the aim of improving the precision of term extraction tools.

In the medical domain, the use of term variants for the same concept can also be a popularization strategy leading to linguistic simplification. The popularization of medical discourse to favor the correct understanding of specialized information by a non-expert audience (such as patients) is a particularly active line of research in terminology. Without claiming to be exhaustive, we can mention, for instance, the works by Delavigne et al. (2007) and Delavigne (2012) about the development of the LexOnco terminological resource collecting popular variants of terms related to the oncology domain; the study by Grøn and Bertels (2018) on the variation of terms used to convey medical information in the different sections of patient electronic health records; and the analysis of Estopà and Montané (2020) on the identification of textual parameters in medical reports that hinder patient understanding, thus leading to severe consequences for their health.

In this context, “diastratic variation” – that is the variation that occurs when it comes to conveying specialized information to non-specialist audiences – is also a central aspect in the context of popularization of medical discourse. Even though its definition in languages for specific purposes still needs to be clarified, Picton and Dury (2017, 59) point out that “the diastratic variation is almost always found in the differences in the terminology used between physicians and that used to address patients”. With the intention of providing a more detailed analysis of this phenomenon, Picton and Dury (2017) investigate diastratic variation in a corpus of nuclear medicine specifically chosen because this field of study is characterized by the interventions of two types of specialists, namely nuclear medicine technologists and nuclear medicine physicians, both having different roles and competencies. Their analysis shows that term variation for the same concept also occurs between different communities of experts in the same field.

2.3 Connotation in medical terminology

Connotation is another linguistic phenomenon that can lead to term variation. The ideal according to which there is only a denotative sense of terms in specialized domains related, for instance, to

the individuals' health and well-being has been overcome by the attestation of a connotative dimension which "peut fort bien s'attacher à un terme au fur et à mesure des usages en discours" (Thoiron and Béjoint 2010, 109). However, as stated in Dury (2012), the role of connotation in specialized languages remains an underrepresented research topic in terminology. Denotation and connotation have been widely discussed (and debated) in the literature with regard to general language (Martinet 1969; Gary-Prieur 1971; Molino 1971; Kerbrat-Orecchioni 1977). In this study, we refer to connotation as defined by Bloomfield (1933, 151-155), i.e. as the set of subjective "supplementary values" attributed to a linguistic sign due to linguistic, cultural, and social factors. In this regard, Bloomfield (1933, 152) affirms that "[i]n the case of scientific terms, we manage to keep the meaning nearly free from connotative factors, though even here we may be unsuccessful [...]". Indeed, as stated in Balliu (2005, 75), we cannot ignore the fact that a medical text always concerns human beings in their most human and fragile aspects. Therefore, medical discourse can imply, more or less latently, a remarkable connotative potential which can also significantly affect interlinguistic tasks such as the translation of specialized medical texts (Vezzani 2023).

In relation to the phenomenon of term variation for medical concepts, Dury's studies (2012, 2013) provide a significant contribution. According to the author, the pejorative connotation anchored to certain terms is the driving force that animates the "neological need" of experts: they sometimes need to redesignate concepts whose designation has been charged, over time, with a de-valoring connotation. Emphasis is placed on diachronic variation, which sheds light on the role of connotation, the obsolescence of terms and the coexistence of variants in specialized discourse. The term *vegetative state*, because of its pejorative connotation, was gradually replaced by the terms *unresponsive wakefulness syndrome* or *UWS*, and *minimally conscious state*, considered by medical experts as more neutral and exact from the scientific viewpoint (Dury 2013, 8). The examination of such cases in the medical context is fundamental and has a significant social impact. Clear evidence of this is provided by Igboanusi et al. (2017), who describe an initiative aimed at promoting the use of appropriate terms in Nigeria's local languages relating to HIV and AIDS, thus reducing the stigmatization and discrimination of people living with this condition, and consequently minimizing the spread of the virus through behavior change. Implicit in these pejorative connotations is also an ideological motive, typically linked to the way a culture or society conceives human beings as opposed to non-human beings (vegetative vs conscious, for instance) or sexually transmitted diseases (shameful and, therefore, taboo).

3. Conceptual evolution and linguistic variation of Body Dysmorphic Disorder

In this section, we describe the analysis of the conceptual and linguistic dimensions of BDD, this being – to our knowledge – the first attempt at a systematic analysis of BDD in terminology.

3.1 Theoretical background and definition of the object of analysis

The theoretical background underlying this study assumes that terminology is a discipline characterized by two dimensions of analysis – conceptual and linguistic – complementary and equally necessary for the representation of specialized knowledge (Costa 2013; Santos and Costa 2015). According to this approach, the terminologist must integrate both the conceptual and the linguistic perspectives to effectively represent the knowledge of a specific subject. The double

dimension implies that both the experts' conceptualizations of a given subject and the discourses produced by them must be considered in terminology work (Carvalho et al. 2016).

To do this, concept and term must be considered to be two autonomous entities which are nevertheless interdependent in terminological work (Silva 2014): the former allows one to conceptualize the world, while the latter allows one to verbalize this conceptualization and to share it with other human beings. In line with ISO 1087: 2019, we adopt the view according to which a term is a designation representing a concept by linguistic means, and a concept is a unit of knowledge created by a unique combination of characteristics.

The identification of the characteristics of a concept by the terminologist can be based on the conceptualization produced by experts in respect of a given topic. By conceptualization we mean the process of abstraction through which “*objects* are grouped into categories. These categories correspond to units of knowledge called *concepts*” (ISO 704: 2022, 3). According to ISO 1087: 2019, objects – defined as “anything perceivable or conceivable”– have *properties* and concepts have *characteristics*. The characteristics of the concept are thus configured as the abstraction of the properties of the object. Revisiting the scheme proposed by Löckinger et al. (2015, 61), the conceptualization process can be summarized as in Figure 1:

Figure 1 - Conceptualization process

Considering the dynamism of specialized knowledge due to scientific and/or technological progress, objects may be subject to reconceptualization. This means that the properties of an object (and consequently the characteristics of a concept, being the abstraction of the properties of an object), for example a pathology, can vary as more knowledge about that object is acquired. The clinical manifestations of a pathology are, for example, properties of the object pathology and are constantly being updated and questioned (see, for example, the reconceptualization process which has characterized Alzheimer's disease in Schermer and Richard (2019)). Reconceptualization can therefore be considered to be the activity performed by domain experts when rethinking objects and their properties. Through abstraction, this rethinking has a direct effect on the concept and on its unique combination of characteristics.

Indeed, the process of reconceptualizing an object has an impact on the unique combination of characteristics that makes up the concept. When there is a change (addition, modification, or suppression) of at least one characteristic of a concept, we face variation. Since the concept is a unit of knowledge created by a *unique* combination of characteristics (ISO 1087: 2019), this means that the change of at least one characteristic leads to the formation of a different concept that represents the new shared specialized knowledge about the object. This theoretical position implies a different perspective concerning conceptual categorization and structuring from the one that was described in the theoretical review section, which posits that there can be conceptual variation within the same concept due to contextual factors, and that a change in conceptual characteristics does not necessarily imply that we are dealing with another concept.

Instead, according to our approach, the characteristics of a concept can vary over time, while concepts evolve into new concepts. For this reason, we prefer to talk about variation of characteristics leading to conceptual evolution (instead of “conceptual variation”). The variation has an impact on the conceptual evolution resulting in the formation of a different concept that supersedes the previous one which then may, in some cases, become obsolete.

The reconceptualization of an object can generate the following two-scenarios on a linguistic level:

- 1) The evolution from concept A to concept B implies a variation of linguistic designation from term A to term B.
- 2) The evolution from concept A to concept B does not involve any changes in linguistic designation.

In the following section, we focus on the first scenario.

3.2 The case of Body Dysmorphic Disorder

As far as BDD is concerned, the analysis of its classification within the biomedical literature and resources illustrates its unstable and changing conceptual and linguistic representation. To conduct this analysis, we collected intraspecialist scientific literature consisting of specialized full texts written by experts for experts, published between 1980⁶ and 2023, freely accessible on the web, and retrieved from authoritative sources, such as PubMed⁷ and the Cochrane Library.⁸ Moreover, we relied upon the information provided in different biomedical Terminological Systems (TSs) for health informatics (ISO 17115: 2020), such as the International Classification of Diseases (ICD), the Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) thesaurus, and the clinical terminology SNOMED CT.

Before delving into the case study, the graphical notations adopted in this paper should be explained. Concepts are capitalized and written between single chevrons (<>), terms are in lowercase and between double quotation marks (“”), characteristics are in brackets ([]), and [characteristic: type=value] is used to indicate the typology of the specific trait of the characteristic.

3.2.1 <Dysmorphophobia>

As Phillips (1991, 1139) points out, “[b]ody dysmorphic disorder is the new name for an old syndrome”. This was described and named for the first time by the psychiatrist E. Morselli as “dysmorphophobia” to designate worries and complaints over an imagined deformity (Morselli

⁶ Date of insertion of the disorder in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders – DSM (American Psychiatric Association 1980).

⁷ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>

⁸ <https://www.cochranelibrary.com>

1886). From an etymological perspective, the term was derived from the Greek “dysmorphia”, meaning ugliness of the body, plus “phobia”, meaning fear. This term first appeared in the *Histories of Herodotus* referring to the myth of the “Ugliest girl in Sparta” (Osman et al. 2011). Other examples of historical references for dysmorphophobia are provided by Mufaddel et al. (2013).

Philips (1991) also describes two related concepts, <Beauty hypochondria> and <Dermatologic hypochondriasis>.⁹ The first one is described by Ladee (1966, cited in Philips 1991, 1139) as follows:

The preoccupation is so exclusively centered on the aspect of the bodily appearance, which is experienced as deformed, repulsive, unacceptable, or ridiculous, that the whole of one’s existence is dominated by this preoccupation and nothing else has any significance anymore.

<Dermatologic hypochondriasis> is another concept referring to a body dysmorphic-disorder-like syndrome that focuses on defects of the skin and hair (Zaidens 1950).

<Dysmorphophobia>, on the other hand, “has generally been defined as a subjective feeling of ugliness or physical defect that the patient thinks are noticeable to others, despite a normal appearance” (Phillips 1991, 1139).

Starting from this natural language definition and considering the features described above as shared properties of the pathology, we assume that the first conceptualization of the object-pathology is abstracted into the concept <Dysmorphophobia> having the following unique combination of characteristics (Figure 2): [subjective feeling: type=fear] + [ugliness/physical defect] + [body], the latter representing the object of the fear. These are considered *essential characteristics* that are “indispensable to understand the concept” (ISO 1087: 2019) associated with the medical condition. The term designating the concept in English language is “dysmorphophobia” and, over time, it has been the object of different interpretations in the intraspecialist literature (Munro and Stewart 1991).

Figure 2 – The concept <Dysmorphophobia> and its linguistic designation

⁹ As mentioned in Mufaddel et al. (2013), the terms “dermatologic hypochondriasis”, “beauty hypochondria”, as well as “dermatophobia” and “dermatologic nondisease” are also often used with reference to “body dysmorphic disorder”.

Regarding the classification of the pathology in biomedical resources, Phillips (1991) highlights that, despite its clear presence in the European literature, the concept of <Dysmorphophobia> is not included in the 8th and 9th edition of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-8 or ICD-9), nor in the first and second edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-I and DSM-II). Indeed, the term “dysmorphophobia” first entered the third edition of the DSM-III in 1980, but only as an example of an atypical somatoform disorder without diagnostic criteria (American Psychiatric Association 1980).

3.2.2 <Body dysmorphic disorder>

Later, the disorder has been the object of a reconceptualization from medical experts involving a shift from one essential characteristic of the concept to another with the consequent attribution of a different designation. A study by Cororve and Gleaves (2001) offers a review of the different reconceptualizations of the disorder carried out by experts since the 1990s. The main point was that the disorder was recognized not as a phobia but rather as an irrational conviction (Cororve and Gleaves 2001), thus leading to the introduction of the term “body dysmorphic disorder” in the revised edition of DSM-III (1987) where the pathology was classified as a nonpsychotic disorder. Indeed, as stated by Munro and Stewart (1991):

Dysmorphophobia is a controversial term. It is not a phobia, reliable data on it are few, and many authors write about it without attempting to define it. DSM-III-R introduced the term “body dysmorphic disorder” to describe a nonpsychotic condition in which there is pathological preoccupation with physical appearance and with the intention of replacing the term “dysmorphophobia”. However, psychiatrists continue to use the word dysmorphophobia, often unaware that it may have several distinct meanings.

However, subsequent studies argued that due to the very low comorbidity with other somatoform disorders, BDD was considered inappropriately classified in that general category (Oosthuizen and Castle 1998).

Phillips et al. (2006b) provide another advance in the identification of the pathology by distinguishing between the concepts of <Delusional body dysmorphic disorder> and <Nondelusional body dysmorphic disorder>. In this sense, Mufaddel et al. (2013) also highlight an inconsistency in BDD classification: “the *DSM-IV* classification of BDD is controversial in that BDD is classified as a somatoform disorder, while its delusional variant is classified as a psychotic disorder”.

Nevertheless, a major advance in its classification is documented in the latest edition of the DSM-V (5th edition), where BDD is classified under the new Obsessive-Compulsive and Related Disorders chapter, considering the high rates of comorbidity between BDD and OCD. In this reclassification, a new diagnostic criterion – repetitive behaviors or mental acts – was included to increase the specificity of BDD diagnosis.

Focusing on the essential characteristics of the concept <Body dysmorphic disorder>, the central turning point in the literature is the shift from the characteristic [fear] to [irrational conviction]. As stated in Rosen (1995, 144), “[t]he essence of the disorder was eventually clarified as not a fear of becoming deformed, but an irrational conviction of already being abnormal and fear of other people’s reactions.” This shift in conceptualization suggests also a broader ideological shift in societal perceptions of body image and mental health. It reflects a transition from framing Body

Dysmorphic Disorder (BDD) as a fear-driven condition to one rooted in a distorted self-perception, highlighting evolving cultural attitudes towards beauty ideals and individual self-image. The change of this essential characteristic of the concept – due to a rethinking of the properties of the same object-pathology – entails a variation of the *unique* combination of characteristics of the new specialized unit of knowledge, thus making the one previously defined for <Dysmorphophobia> obsolete. In other words, the replacement of the characteristic [fear] with [irrational conviction], as well as the addition of other characteristics for the identification of the BDD diagnostic criteria, involves an evolution of the concept from <Dysmorphophobia> to <Body dysmorphic disorder>. Figure 3 summarizes (and simplifies)¹⁰ the new conceptualization.

Figure 3 – The concept <Body dysmorphic disorder> and its linguistic designation

As far as the linguistic dimension is concerned, this reconceptualization involves a term variation from “dysmorphophobia” to “body dysmorphic disorder”, although – as mentioned in Munro and Stewart (1991) – the two terms continue to coexist in medical discourse and may be considered quasi-synonyms since they are interchangeable only in some contexts (ISO 704: 2022).

With the aim of providing an exhaustive description of the current representation of BDD, different biomedical terminological systems (TSS) for health informatics (ISO 17115: 2020) have been analysed, showing several inconsistencies in the conceptual and linguistic representation of the disorder. In Table 1, we report the position of the concept <Body Dysmorphic Disorder> (BDD) in the hierarchies of four resources. For each resource, we report the identifier of BDD within the resource, the immediate superordinate concept of BDD, and the super-superordinate concept.

Resource	Identifier	Superordinate concept	Super-superordinate concept
ICD-10	F45.2	<Hypochondriacal disorder>	<Somatoform Disorders>
ICD-11	6B21	<Obsessive-compulsive or related disorder>	<Mental, behavioural or neurodevelopmental disorders>
SNOMED	SCTID 83482000	<Hypochondriasis>	<Somatoform disorders>
MeSH	F03.875.149	<Somatoform Disorders>	<Mental Disorders>

¹⁰ By simplification we mean the fact that, for this analysis, we have chosen the least number of characteristics necessary to be able to highlight the difference between the two concepts.

Table 1 – Hierarchical representation of <Body Dysmorphic Disorder> in four biomedical TSs.

As shown in the table, in the 10th edition of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10) BDD is not an independent diagnostic category, being listed under the concept <Hypochondriacal Disorder>, and its symptoms are referred to under several other diagnostic categories, potentially giving rise to diagnostic confusion and inappropriate treatment (Veale and Matsunaga 2014). For this reason, in the new ICD-11 edition that came into effect on the 1st of January 2022, the <Body Dysmorphic Disorder> is recognized as a separate diagnosis from <Hypochondriasis>, and both are subsumed under a new Obsessive–Compulsive and Related Disorders chapter (Stein et al. 2016). In SNOMED CT, BDD is still classified as a subtype of the concept <Hypochondriasis>, in turn subordinate to the supertype <Somatoform Disorder>. Finally, in the Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) thesaurus, BDD is classified as a separate concept from <Hypochondriasis>, and both are subordinated to the general concept <Somatoform Disorders>. Since these resources are widely used for supporting e-Health tools and services aiming at enhancing the prevention, diagnosis, treatment, and monitoring of diseases (Eysenbach 2001), the variability of BDD representation and classification within these different TSs can increase the chance of its misdiagnosis and potentially lead to inappropriate medical treatment.

4. Dissemination of BDD

Mass media are one of the most powerful means for the dissemination of information related to the health and well-being of individuals (Wakefield et al. 2010). Therefore, the terminology used by them has a strong impact on the public. This is even more tangible when the objects of dissemination are relatively under-/misdiagnosed medical conditions, such as BDD. Against this backdrop, we present a corpus of mass-media articles created to investigate the popular discourse about BDD, under the hypothesis that this can influence the social perception of the pathology, and consequently, the importance that is attributed to its identification, diagnosis, and treatment. The corpus under analysis was created with Sketch Engine¹¹ (Kilgariff et al. 2014). We first selected 11 English-language newspapers which, according to the data provided by the World Association of Newspapers and News Publishers,¹² rank as the most popular and have the largest circulation in the world. The selected newspapers are the following: The New York Times, The Washington Post, The Guardian, The Wall Street Journal, Daily Mail, The Times of India, Metro, The Sun, The Times, The Australian, and BCC News. These newspapers range from gossip and news items to financial affairs, and cover several diatopic varieties of English, thus providing a general overview of the language.

Once the selection of the newspapers was completed, we used the *Web search*¹³ function in Sketch Engine, which allows the input of keywords (ranging from 3 to 20) to define the topic of the new corpus. For the purposes of this study, we included the terms “body dysmorphic disorder”, “dysmorphophobia” and “ugliness”, the latter being a characteristic shared by both concepts (see section 3 above). We then manually set the following three criteria:

1. Maximum number of URLs for search: 100 (the maximum allowed by the software);
2. Seed words in search: 2, so that the tool could find all the documents containing at least 2 of the aforementioned terms.

¹¹ <https://www.sketchengine.eu>.

¹² <https://wan-ifra.org>.

¹³ <https://www.sketchengine.eu/blog/build-a-corpus-from-the-web/>.

3. Sites list: links to the 11 newspapers mentioned above to limit the search for the 3 key terms to the selected newspapers.

The so created corpus (named “BDD newspapers”) contains 550 documents (approximately 640,000 tokens). We then used the *Keyword and term extraction*¹⁴ function to identify the relevant terms in our corpus. The operation was performed on the basis of automatic contrastive analysis of the occurrences between the BDD newspaper corpus (focus corpus) and the English Web 2020 (enTenTen20)¹⁵ used as a reference corpus. This method allowed us to automatically extract a list of candidate terms (single- and multi-word terms) which were then manually checked. Through this process, we were able to isolate term variants referring to BDD, as well as terminological neologisms emerged with reference to this medical condition.

Among the different designations identified, the terms “imagined ugliness” or “imagined ugliness syndrome” seem relevant in this context since they often appear as variants of BDD. See, for example, the following excerpt from a 1991 New York Times article:

(1) Each of these people was suffering from what psychiatrists call body dysmorphic disorder, or imagined ugliness, a relatively new formal diagnosis.¹⁶

However, as stated on the Body Dysmorphic Disorder Foundation website:¹⁷

The media sometimes refer to BDD as “imagined ugliness syndrome”. This isn’t particularly helpful as the ugliness is very real to the individual concerned, and does not reflect the severe distress that BDD can cause.¹⁸

The use of the adjective “imagined” (instead of, for example, “perceived”) can therefore have a negative impact on the perception of the disorder itself and consequently on the importance attributed to it. As mentioned in section 3, the specificity of the disorder (and the reason for its reconceptualization) lies in the fact that people affected by BDD perceive and are irrationally convinced that they have defects or flaws in appearance. For this reason, referring to this pathology in terms of “imagination” does not reflect the real perception of patients and the significant suffering resulting from it. In this regard, a Metro article published in 2015 points out:

(2) The disorder has been called imagined ugliness syndrome in the past, but for the individual the ugliness is very real. In extreme cases, the intensity of the distress and isolation can drive people with BDD to suicide.¹⁹

We can also argue that these data reflect an underlying ideology whereby mental conditions are not real but imagined, thereby somehow downgrading a very serious condition to a sort of whim.

¹⁴ <https://www.sketchengine.eu/guide/keywords-and-term-extraction/>.

¹⁵ For a detailed description of this corpus: <https://www.sketchengine.eu/ententen-english-corpus/>.

¹⁶ <https://www.nytimes.com/1991/10/02/health/when-ugliness-is-only-in-patient-s-eye-body-image-can-reflect-mental-disorder.html?searchResultPosition=21>.

¹⁷ BDD foundation was founded in 2006 based in the UK. The foundation's goal is to advance education and understanding of BDD, as well as raise awareness, reduce stigma, discrimination and isolation caused by BDD: <https://bddfoundation.org/about/about-us/>.

¹⁸ <https://bddfoundation.org/information/what-is-bdd/>.

¹⁹ <https://metro.co.uk/2015/10/05/artist-with-body-dysmorphic-disorder-sees-herself-with-a-face-tumour-that-doesnt-exist-5422027/>.

Indeed, from an historical viewpoint, mental illnesses have often been stigmatized and misunderstood, leading to the marginalization of individuals suffering from such conditions.²⁰ Additionally, there still exists a cultural tendency to prioritize physical health over mental well-being, perpetuated by societal norms that prioritize productivity and physical appearance. An indication of this can be seen, for example, in one of the definitions of mental health provided by the World Health Organization (WHO):

[..] state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community (World Health Organization 2004, 59).

Indeed, as stated in Hommel and Beste (2021), this definition reflects at least two ideological premises:

[..] the criteria of “productive and fruitful work” and especially the last part of the sentence “able to make a contribution to his or her community”, introduce the societal utility of the individual as a criterion for judging mental health, which renders the concept of mental health an ideological rather than a medical or psychological judgment.

Furthermore, the lack of understanding and empathy towards mental health issues leads to the misconception that they are merely a result of personal weakness or moral failing, rather than legitimate medical conditions. This ideology not only undermines the severity of mental disorders but also iterates harmful stereotypes and prevents individuals from seeking the help they need.

In this regard, the study by Ribeiro (2017) points out that many patients feel embarrassed about their concerns and typically find it difficult to seek psychiatric assistance, turning instead to cosmetic and surgical treatments. Indeed, in the corpus being analyzed, two terminological neologisms “snapchat dysmorphia” and “zoom dysmorphia” were identified:

(3) Although the media have coined various terms for BDD over the years such as “snapchat dysmorphia” or “facial dysmorphia”, they are all examples of the same condition: Body Dysmorphic Disorder.²¹

(4) What the doctor is describing is a condition experts have described as “zoom dysmorphia”. This phenomenon erupted during the Covid pandemic, when many Americans began to work from home.²²

These two terms were introduced very recently: “snapchat dysmorphia” (Ramphul and Mejias 2018) in 2018 and “zoom dysmorphia” (Rice et al. 2021) in 2021, respectively. Both reflect the evolution of the disorder in reference to technological progress. The term “snapchat dysmorphia” describes a trend of patients seeking plastic surgeries to mimic filtered pictures, often presenting unrealistic and unattainable looks that may be a causal factor in triggering BDD (Ramphul and Mejias 2018). The term “zoom dysmorphia” emerged during the COVID-19 pandemic to identify the increasing requests for cosmetic procedures by patients to improve their (perceived) distorted

²⁰ <https://www.psychiatry.org/patients-families/stigma-and-discrimination>.

²¹ <https://metro.co.uk/2021/05/21/experts-say-facial-dysmorphia-is-on-the-rise-but-what-is-it-14610924/>.

²² <https://www.dailymail.co.uk/health/article-11908051/Nose-jobs-facial-augmentation-plastic-surgery-choice.html>.

appearance on video-conferencing calls (Rice et al. 2021). These terms also reflect evolving societal ideologies regarding beauty standards and self-image in the digital age, underscoring the need of examining and challenging those ideologies that sustain unrealistic beauty ideals and contribute to mental health conditions.

As we observed, term variations result from reconceptualizations that impact popularized discourses. This impact may be both negative and positive. The negative aspect arises from the fact that variations can be obstacles to precise communication. However, precision is not always the primary goal. The UN 2030 Agenda emphasizes the need to adapt language registers and terminological resources for citizens, with ‘science with and for society’ being one of the priorities. This implies that science must transition from the scientific sphere to non-scientific information contexts: “The democratization of science entails the public having greater influence over science and that influence being shared more equally among members of the public” (Kurtulmuş 2023). The study we conducted has an influence on the philosophy of the terminological resource, as we will need to reflect on the various points of view. Each of them represents a different ideology concerning the organization, structure, and description of the terminological data.

5. Conclusions and perspectives

This paper illustrates a multilevel analysis of the specialized and popular medical discourse on BDD. In particular, the first research objective discussed is the analysis of the reconceptualization of this pathology and the transition from the concept of <Dysmorphophobia> to <Body dysmorphic disorder>, this evolution being due to the suppression of the essential characteristic [fear] and its replacement with [irrational conviction]. On the linguistic level, we observed that this reconceptualization involved the variation of the terms used to designate the concepts, namely “dysmorphophobia” and “body dysmorphic disorder”, both still coexisting in specialized medical discourse. The second research objective was rather aimed at investigating the popular discourse about BDD and at analyzing how information about BDD is disseminated to non-experts, as well as the ideological implications of this process.

In our future research, we intend to investigate on the perception of the different designations of the disorder among non-experts. Our idea is to conduct a public survey with the aim to identify relevant data in terms of negative connotations attributed to the different term variants used to refer to the pathology. This survey will be addressed to English, French, Portuguese, and Italian participants to conduct a cross-linguistic and cross-cultural fine-grained analysis of the perception of this medical condition. Furthermore, based on the analysis proposed by Piccini et. al (2023), we intend to design and develop the first BDD terminological knowledge base complying with the FAIR terminology paradigm (Vezzani 2022). This resource will serve the purpose of representing, organizing, sharing, and reusing the current and future knowledge regarding this subject for both experts and non-experts, contributing to the quality of the specialized discourses and making BDD more visible and, consequently, more comprehensible to the society.

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